

MATERIALS SCIENCE AND MECHANICS OF MACHINES

INCREASING THE FATIGUE STRENGTH OF MACHINE PARTS USING SURFACE ENGINEERING METHODS

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Abstract

The purpose of the work is to increase fatigue resistance and durability of machine parts due to various methods of surface action. To solve it, studies of the effect on the surface condition of various variants of combined methods of mechanical processing, cementation and surface plastic deformation, as well as a modern method of bombarding the surface layer with low-energy ions were carried out. It was established that after grinding the surface before cementation, and not after, it increases by 41% endurance limit (σ_{-1}) of 20X2H4A steel, as compressive stresses during cementation reduce the effect of harmful tensile stresses that occur during grinding. An even greater increase in σ_{-1} is achieved after final blasting due to additional compressive stresses and significant surface smoothing during surface plastic deformation - slandering. The high efficiency of ion bombardment of the surface of 40X and 65Г steels is shown, under the influence of which the grains in the thin surface layer are very finely ground (from 50 μm to 600 nm), a developed substructure is formed, defects are "healed", and the surface roughness is significantly reduced.

These changes in the state of the surface contributed to resistance to fatigue failure and a significant increase in the durability of the products.

Keywords: mechanical processing, shot peening, ion bombardment, surface roughness, substructure, cyclic durability

Introduction

As you know, any external impact on the material of a part occurs through its surface and most destructive processes begin in the surface layers. The service life of machines is largely determined by the quality of the surface of machine parts. The surface condition significantly affects the volumetric mechanical properties of products, and, first of all, resistance to fatigue failure, since a fatigue crack usually initiates from the surface or in surface layers.

Due to the increasing complexity of modern structures, operating modes, and the intensification of work processes of mechanisms and machines, the ability of parts to resist fatigue failure is of particular importance. It should be emphasized that fatigue develops at stress levels significantly below the yield strength of the material (even before the first signs of plastic deformation appear) and leads to a decrease in service life. This is confirmed by statistics - more than 80% of failures of machine parts occur due to destruction due to the development of fatigue processes [1]. Fatigue damage is local, not accompanied by any visible effects and is therefore especially dangerous. Therefore, solving the issue of increasing fatigue strength is relevant.

Analysis of publications.

One of the important features of the functioning of machine parts and mechanisms is the presence of a significant number of stress concentrators, which have a significant impact on the performance parameters of products [2]. In this regard, it is necessary to provide

for the possibility of "technological compensation" for the presence of concentrators in order to minimize their negative impact on the reliability of the product during operation under conditions of shifting power loads. These problems are solved by surface engineering methods.

The quality of the surface is determined by the microgeometry of irregularities, the sign of stresses, chemical composition, grain size, and structural changes that occur during the processing of parts [3,4]. One of the main indicators of fatigue strength - the endurance limit - strongly depends on the quality of the surface layer, the presence of microcracks in it, and their size. Since, under repeated force stresses, the onset of fracture is associated with the formation of a surface crack, it is quite obvious that as the surface roughness decreases, the fatigue resistance increases. Thus, according to work [4], the endurance limit of samples made of low-strength steel, the surface of which was not treated after rolling, is 70% of the endurance limit of finely polished samples. For high-strength steel, which is more sensitive to local stresses, this ratio is significantly lower and amounts to only 35%. Reducing the depth of depressions and micro-roughnesses, which are stress concentrators and cause the appearance of fatigue cracks, leads to increased fatigue life.

To increase the fatigue strength of a wide range of machine parts, surface plastic deformation (SPD) is widely used. The authors [5] have convincingly shown

that SPD using a striker tool for parts made of normalized steel 40X leads to an increase in the level of compressive macrostresses by more than 6 times. At the same time, durability increases by ~ 5 times.

With such types of hardening surface treatment as carburization and nitriding, significant compressive stresses arise on the surface, preventing the initiation of fatigue cracks. The work [6] notes that in parts after carburization (with subsequent hardening and low tempering), depending on the carbon concentration in the hardened layer, the value of these stresses reaches 300–400 MPa, and after nitriding they increase to 700–800 MPa. As a result, the endurance limit increases by 1.3 - 1.5 times, respectively.

Modern and effective methods of processing the surface layer, which radically change its structural-stress state and microgeometry, include ultrasonic impact treatment (UIT), frictional hardening, and ion-plasma technologies (CIB method). Using these surface modification methods, the improvement in the fatigue characteristics of the material can accordingly be explained by the submicro- and nanostructuring of a thin surface layer, an increase in the density of defects in the crystal structure and the creation of compressive stresses.

The authors of [7] note that after ultrasonic impact treatment (UIT) of C τ 3 steel, the formation of a sub-grain structure in the surface layer and the appearance of compressive macrostresses led to an increase in the endurance limit by 50%, and the durability increased by an order of magnitude.

The performance of machine parts under cyclic loads is significantly influenced by technological methods of surface hardening using highly concentrated energy sources. The source [8] states that frictional hardening of the surface prevents the further development of existing cracks and the formation of new ones. On the surface of the metal (carbon, structural steels and cast irons) a hardened layer 0.1–0.4 mm thick with a nanocrystalline structure, surface roughness $R_a = 0.4\text{--}0.63 \mu\text{m}$ is formed, which has increased fatigue and corrosion-fatigue strength. The durability of parts after friction hardening of the surface increases to 50%. The authors of work [9] came to a similar conclusion, stating that after friction treatment, due to the formation of a specific structurally stressed state of the metal, characterized by an increased dislocation density, refined grain, and the presence of residual compressive stresses, the fatigue strength of steels 45, 40 X and V8A both in air and in a corrosive environment (3% aqueous NaCl solution). The increase in durability is 1.3 - 1.6 times in air and 3.4 - 6.5 times in a corrosive environment.

The influence of nanostructured surface layers on increasing cyclic durability became the subject of research in works [10 - 13]. The authors of [10-12] point to a significant increase in fatigue strength after the formation of a nanocrystalline layer on the surface as a result of ion bombardment. At the same time, the results of [13] indicate that ion bombardment, while providing a nanostructure to the surface of steel products, leads to only a very slight increase in the endurance limit σ_{-1}

($\sim 5\%$). Such controversial findings require further research in this innovative direction, arouse considerable interest and are certainly relevant. The development of provisions on the possibility of healing discontinuities that arise in the metal during cyclic loading is also an important aspect in solving the problem of increasing the durability of products.

Purpose and objectives of the study

The purpose of this work is to increase fatigue resistance and increase the durability of machine parts by modifying the surface.

The objectives of the research are to study the influence of the surface condition after various processing methods (mechanical in combination with chemical-thermal, ion bombardment) on fatigue strength, which will make it possible to predict the durability of products.

Material and research methods

Case-hardened steel 20X2H4A, upgradeable steel 40X, spring steel 65Г were studied.

Different methods of surface treatment were chosen for the study: carburizing, mechanical processing (grinding and polishing), shot peening (SPD) and ion bombardment.

Shot blasting of gear teeth was carried out in a pneumatic chamber according to the following mode: air pressure 5 atm, shot with a diameter of 0.6 - 0.8 mm, distance from the nozzle 200 mm, processing time 5 minutes. The surface roughness and profile were determined using a TR200 profilometer according to the ISO 4287-1997 standard. The measurement error for R_a did not exceed 10%.

Fatigue tests were performed on a MUI-6000 machine using a symmetrical bending with rotation scheme. The test base was 10^7 loading cycles. The test samples had a working part shortened due to the transition sections, which made it possible to reduce warping (no more than 0.05 mm) and increase rigidity. In order to obtain reliable results for each state of the material, at least 10 samples were subject to testing.

The treatment of fatigue samples with low-energy (<3 keV) titanium ions was carried out on a Bulat-3t installation in an argon atmosphere, at a pressure of 0.133 Pa, a current of 95-100 A, and a voltage of 900-1100 V. Treatment time was 1.5 min. Selection of parameterson bombardment (IB) mode prevented sample heating. To ensure uniform surface treatment, the samples were rotated using a planetary mechanism.

In order to obtain the distribution of components and their identification in the surface layers of samples treated with ion bombardment, micro-X-ray spectral analysis was used. The stressed state of the surface layer was determined using a DRON-3 diffractometer.

Research results

The influence of various types of mechanical processing on the endurance limit and durability of products made of case-hardened steels

Case-hardened steel 20X2H4A, which is widely used for large critical parts, in particular heavily loaded gears operating under high alternating stresses and friction conditions.

Carburization mode: temperature 930°C, holding for 10 hours, cooling to 820°C, quenching in oil, low

tempering 180-200°C, effective layer thickness 1.3 – 1.5 mm. After cementation, a high-strength, brittle surface state is realized, for which roughness indicators are especially important, since even minor irregularities are stress concentrators and their relaxation occurs not due to local plastic deformations, but due to the occurrence of microcracks. Taking these provisions into account, the surface of the samples for testing for fatigue strength was processed according to three options:

1. Turning with an allowance for grinding to a depth of 0.2 mm per side, cementation + hardening + low tempering, grinding to a depth of 0.2 mm.

2. Turning, grinding, chemical-thermal treatment, polishing to nominal size.

3. Turning, grinding, chemical-thermal treatment, polishing, shot blasting.

Option 1 corresponds to the gear manufacturing technology commonly used in practice. But, as is

known, during the grinding process, residual tensile stresses and structural heterogeneity are created in the surface layer after carburization due to phase transformations.

Option 2 eliminates the harmful effects of residual stresses from grinding, since it was carried out before carburization. In option 3, the goal was to assess the effect of surface plastic deformation.

Fig. 1 shows the surface profiles of the samples after the indicated processing options.

As can be seen, after grinding (Fig. 1, a) the surface profile is characterized by deep protrusions and depressions. Mechanical polishing leads to a significant deep protrusions and depressions. Mechanical polishing leads to a significant smoothing of the protrusions and a significant reduction in surface roughness (Fig. 1, b). Shot treatment due to work hardening slightly worsens the surface roughness (Fig. 1, c).

Fig.1 Profiles and surface roughness of samples after different processing options: a – grinding; b – polishing; c – shot blasting.

Based on the test results, fatigue curves were constructed (Fig. 2.)

Fig.2 Fatigue curves of specimens made of steel 20X2H4A after various types of surface treatment

Table 1 shows the values of the endurance limits of samples obtained after various options for their surface treatment.

Table 1

Values of endurance limits of tested sample variants

No option	Endurance limit σ_{-1} , MPA	Increase in endurance limit, %
1	630	100*
2	890	141
3	990	157

*Option 1 is accepted as 100%

The appearance of the curves in Fig. 2 indicates that grinding before carburization and polishing after (processing option 2) led to a significant decrease in surface roughness (Fig. 1, b) and an increase in the limit endurance by 41%. The durability of the samples under overloads has also increased noticeably. This is indicated by the fact that the left inclined branch of the curve of option 2 is located significantly more to the right than the section of the inclined branch of the curve of option 1 at the same stress level.

Shot blasting of the surface increased the endurance limit by another 16% (up to 57%) and increased durability further (option 3, Fig. 2). This fact can be explained by the appearance of internal residual compressive stresses recorded by us (about 550 MPa), as well as the almost complete destruction of the structural heterogeneity of the surface in the process of plastic deformation during shot peening. In addition, as is known, during surface plastic deformation, positive changes in the intragranular structure occur (crushing of blocks, increase in dislocation density), which contributes to surface hardening. The resulting depressions from the shot (diameter 0.8 mm), although they increase its roughness, but due to their rounded shape and small penetration into the very hard martensitic structure of the surface after chemical

treatment, are not significant stress concentrators - sources of fatigue crack development.

The tests carried out showed the effectiveness of not only the final surface plastic deformation, but also the grinding of samples before carburization. In addition, the use of option 2, where possible, reduces the surface treatment process.

Ion bombardment as one of the modern methods for increasing the cyclic durability of products

The experiments were performed on samples made of steels 40X and 65Г. These steels were chosen for practical reasons. 40X steel is used to make axles, connecting rods, gears, shafts, that is, parts that are used under repeated cyclic loads. Steel 65Г is spring-steel, and one of the main requirements for these products is high fatigue strength.

The surface condition of 40X steel samples after ion bombardment (IB) is illustrated in Fig. 3.

Before bombardment, the average grain size corresponded to 50 μm , and after IB, a developed substructure with a grain size of 600-800 nm and wide grain boundaries (Fig. 3). The formed cellular dislocation substructure (Fig. 4, b), characterized by a low dislocation density in the cell body and significant misorientation.

Fig. 3 Sample made of steel 40X (hardening + high tempering) after IB;
× 15000.

Fig. 4 Substructure of steel before (a) and after (b) IB; × 15000.

Using the method of micro-X-ray spectral analysis, a chemical deposit on the surface with a method for identifying titanium was identified, which could be consumed during the bombardment and fall into power. The results showed that the hardness of

titanium on the surface is only 0.35% (Fig. 5, a). Titanium is present in the surrounding spots, which is confirmed by a diffraction pattern and elemental analysis of one of them (Fig. 5, b).

Інформація			
Напруження (кВ) 20.0			
Сума % 100.0			
Елемент	К	Інт.	С %
Fe	К	34605	98.74
Mn	К	252	0.72
Ti	К	815	0.35
Si	К	342	0.18

a

Інформація			
Напруження (кВ) 20.0			
Сума % 100.0			
Елемент	К	Інт.	С, %
Ti	К	4710	97.03
Fe	К	647	2.75
Si	К	347	0.17

b

Fig. 5 Chemical and elemental composition of the surface of the sample(a) and composition of titanium drops (b) after IB.

Drops of titanium fall into areas of surface irregularities and discontinuities (pores, cavities, microcracks), “heal” them (Fig. 6) and reduce the number of stress concentrators.

Fig. 6 A drop of Ti that flogged into a recess on the surface during IS; $\times 10000$

However, despite the presence of a droplet phase of titanium and a developed substructure, the roughness after IB decreases very significantly (Fig. 7), which indicates a shallow depth of the surface relief.

Similar structural changes occurred in steel 65 Γ (hardening. + medium tempering) after IB.

Reduction of roughness, “healing of surface defects, significant grain refinement and the presence of a developed substructure in the surface layer could not but affect the durability of products.

Fig. 7 Surface roughness sample made of 40X steel:
a – before IB, b – after IB

The results of cyclic durability tests are shown in Table 2. As can be seen from the table, at a stress of 380 MPa, a sample made of 40X steel without IB failed after 297,600 cycles, and after IB it withstood 1,000,000 cycles without destruction. An increase in stress to 430 MPa (by 14%) led to destruction, but at the same time the durability increased by ~ 1.5 times. An even greater increase in cyclic durability is recorded for samples made of 60G steel: without IB they failed after 937,440 cycles at a stress of 380 MPa. After IB,

even with an increase in stress by 44% - up to 550 MPa (the maximum for the diameter of the tested samples), they withstood more than 1 million cycles without destruction.

Thus, it has been convincingly shown that surface treatment using one of the modern methods - bombardment with low-energy ions - significantly increases the fatigue resistance of products under cyclic loads.

Table 2

Impact of information security on cyclic durability

Material and processing	Stress magnitude, MPa	Number of cycles before failure	Test result
Steel 40X, original	380	297600	collapsed
Steel 40X, original + IB	380	1000000	didn't collapse
Steel 40X, original + IB	430	453840	collapsed
Steel 65, original	380	937440	collapsed
Steel 65, original+ IB	550	1116000	didn't collapse

Conclusions

1. Research has shown that grinding the surface before carburization (and not after) increases the endurance limit of high-strength steel 20X2H4A with a brittle martensitic structure after hardening by 40%.

2. Subsequent fine polishing and shot peening of the cemented layer further increases the resistance to fatigue failure due to a significant reduction in surface roughness and the creation of favorable compressive stresses.

3. The greatest effect of increasing the cyclic durability of products was recorded after bombarding a thin surface layer with low-energy ions and is achieved by significant grain refinement, the formation of a developed substructure, an increase in dislocation density, and "healing" of surface defects, which are local stress concentrators and potential sources of microcrack formation.

4. When addressing issues of technological support and improving the quality of machine parts operating under cyclic loading conditions, one should choose processing processes that will ensure the characteristics of the surface layer, guaranteeing the durability of the product.

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